

Neuroticism and its Effect on Information Seeking Behavior: A Study of Academic Librarians in Federal Universities

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ABSTRACT

Neuroticism which experts' call one of the "Big Five" personality traits is a set of common characteristics that are found around the world most often. This study therefore investigated the impact of neuroticism as a trait on the information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in Federal universities in Nigeria. It adopted a survey research design while random sampling technique was used to obtain a sampled population of 665 academic librarians from 42 federal universities in Nigeria. The major instrument use for data collection was a self-constructed Likert type structured four point questionnaires. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics tools of mean, frequencies and percentiles while the null hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis of the correlation coefficient at a 0.05 level of significance. The outcome of the study did reveal that there is statistical significant ($P>0.5$) correlation between neuroticism and information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in studied federal universities. Based on the findings, the study recommended among other things; the that management of federal university libraries should make provision for a separate section of library; equipped with state of the art facilities exclusively for academic librarians for effective research and to enhance their academic activities as well as that library management and the university should adjust the working hours of academic librarians to accommodate their personal responsibilities as a way of easing work created stress.

Keywords: Information Seeking Behaviour, Information, Personality trait, Neuroticism, Academic Librarian

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INTRODUCTION

Librarians by profession are information managers and driving force to accessing to information and knowledge dissemination. In today's world, information has become the greatest and the most sought for asset as the globe is ruled by information. The painstaking situation is that the globe has experienced exponential growth of Information with most in digital form powered by the information super highway

called the internet. On the other hand, academic librarians who have found themselves in the forefront of research and supporting the tripartite role of universities which are, teaching/learning, research and extension are faced with tripartite challenges of satisfying the information needs of their teeming users, providing information for faculty members and involving in personal research and publications under the publish or you perish sarcasm. Under these scenarios, academic librarians work with high expectations to meet up all assigned responsibilities which may affect their information seeking behaviors. As noted by Uhegbu (2007), information seeking behavior is the way someone who uses information conducts self or behaves while searching, obtaining or acquiring the needed information. He revealed that utterances, gesture, anger, anxiety, eagerness, reluctance, zeal or any other attribute displayed by an information user in his efforts to locate, acquire or receive news, data, stories or anything that may inform or misinform his knowledge or understanding of something, constitute seeking behavior. According to Singh and Satija (2016), information seeking is a basic activity indulged in by all people and manifested through a particular way of behavior. It is an aspect of scholarly work most interesting to academic libraries who strive to develop collections services and organizational structures that facilitate seeking of information. In fact, information seeking behavior is an area of dynamic interest among academic librarians, as they make active and intentional attempts to seek up to date information from the library resources. In recent time as a result of global information explosion, academic librarians who in most cases double as lecturers information seeking behaviors have been affected by the use of online information sources and services, such as electronic journals, databases, directories and search engines. Academic Librarians also use the Web browsers due to the Web's convenience and access to vast information sources. Statistics did show that every day over 10,000 new Web sites are launched, and over 3.5 billion e-mail messages shoot across the net daily (Klobas, 2016). Furthermore, Librarians are also utilizing directories and search engines to obtain information in any subject both for themselves and other library users, while in the words of Baruchson (2015), electronic journals, databases and on-line services have transformed access to information making information readily available.

In the cause of performing this information searching as a result of the burdensome of the work, some librarians do exhibit neurosis tendency also known as neuroticism. Neuroticism according to Powell (2023) is the trait disposition to experience negative effects, including anger, anxiety, self-consciousness, irritability, emotional instability, and depression. As explained by Powell (2023), sometimes neurotic behaviors arise because one literally have a neurotic personality also called neuroticism, a personality type that cannot be diagnose as a medical problem rather seen and call by experts as one of the "Big Five" personality traits that include extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness to experience.

The aim of this study is to investigate the impact of neuroticism on academic librarians' information seeking behavior. This study has become imperative as there is dearth of literature in this field of knowledge in this part of the globe to the best of knowledge of the researcher, therefore this study, intend to bridge this gap and to create the desired awareness among academic librarians in federal universities in Nigeria in particular and librarians in general of the existence of such traits.

1.2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of this study are to:

- i. Identify factors that influence information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in federal universities;
- ii. To ascertain challenges faced by academic librarians in these federal universities in their information seeking behaviour,
- iii. Identify those neuroticism traits displayed by academic librarians in their information seeking behaviour, and
- iv. Determine correlation between neuroticism and information seeking behaviour of the academic librarians.

1.3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To realize these objectives, the study was guided by the following two Research Questions:

- i. What factors influence information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in federal universities?
- ii. What are the challenges militating against of information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in federal universities?
- iii. What are the Neuroticism traits displayed by academic librarians in federal universities in their information seeking behaviour?
- iv. What is the correlation between neuroticism and information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in these federal universities?

1.4. HYPOTHESIS

The study also tested one null hypothesis

- i. H01. There is no statistical significant ($>p=0.05$) correlation between neuroticism and information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in federal universities in Nigeria.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. CONCEPTUAL OVERVIEW

2.1.2. NEUROTICISM

According to Widiger and Oltmanns (2017), neuroticism is the trait disposition to experience negative effects, including anger, anxiety, self-consciousness, irritability, emotional instability, and depression.

In this regard persons with elevated levels of neuroticism respond poorly to environmental stress, interpret ordinary situations as threatening, and can experience minor frustrations as hopelessly overwhelming. While Arlin (2023) describes it as a core personality trait characterized by emotional instability, irritability, anxiety, self-doubt, depression, and other negative feelings noting that like other personality traits, it exists on a continuum. Which means that one with the trait can be high, low, or somewhere in the middle in terms of this trait. In other words, neuroticism is a trait that reflects a person's level of emotional stability. It is therefore seen as a negative personality trait involving negative emotions, poor self-regulation and trouble dealing with stress, a strong reaction to perceived threats, and the tendency to complain.

As explained by Powell (2023), sometimes neurotic behaviors arise because one literally has a neurotic personality also called neuroticism, a personality type that cannot be diagnose as a medical problem rather seen and call by experts as one of the "Big Five" personality traits that include extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness to experience, a set of common characteristics that are found around the world most often. As reported by WebMD (2023), the American Psychiatric Association in 1980 expunged the term neurosis from its diagnostic manual in an effort to standardize the criteria for mental illnesses. Presently, neurosis is not a stand-alone mental condition rather doctors most often put its symptoms in the same category as anxiety disorder. In other words, what used to be called neurosis now falls under the umbrella of anxiety. Suffice it to say, that Neurotic means one afflicted by neurosis, a word that has been in use since the 1700s to describe mental, emotional, or physical reactions that are drastic and irrational. At its root, a neurotic behavior is an automatic, unconscious effort to manage deep anxiety.

There are always two sides to personality traits and neuroticism being one is not an exemption. To this end, from the negative point of view, people with neurotic personalities are more likely to indulge in smoking, drug abuse and having eating disorders and social supports among other vices. In the context of this study, the area of focus is in the positive hence, the healthy aspect of neurotic tendencies. That being the case, it is pertinent to state that people with a healthy dose of neurotic tendencies which is a balanced personality can utilize it for their gains and that of the society as they can channel their anxiety about a deadline at work to frame it as a chance to earn a promotion or to team up with fellow staff (Widiger and Oltmanns, 2017). On a lighter mood, just like worries about one's health could motivate him or her to eat well and get involved in physical exercises.

2.1.2. INFORMATION AND INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOR

Information is news or knowledge communicated through the spoken or written word, facts or data. It can also mean knowledge gathered through reading or through instructions. Information exists as an idea in people, data in computer files or in various other forms. These ideas are conveyed and used for the achievement of specific purposes. Information is messages transmitted orally or written or as data presented in a document (Ebbighausen, 2011). Information can be used to mean man's accumulated knowledge in all subjects, in all forms and from all sources that could help users to make rational decisions. Information is central to all activities and very essential to human survival. It is crucial in every

research work and it is vital to the development of any society (Oziri, Unegbu and Ndulaka, 2023). According to Unegbu, Opara and Emuchay (2023), information is viewed as answers to questions that begin with such words as who, what, where, when and how many. This indicates that it could be knowledge one gets about someone or something as well as factors or details about a subject.

As posited by Uhegbu (2007), information seeking behavior is the way an information user conducts oneself or acts when looking for, receiving or acquiring information. The author further states that utterances, gesture, anger, anxiety, eagerness, reluctance, zeal or any other attribute displayed by an information user in his efforts to purchase, acquire or receive news, data, stories or anything that may inform or misinform his knowledge or understanding of something constitute seeking behavior. Wilson (1981) describes information seeking behaviour as the totality of human behavior in relation to source and channels of information, including both active and passive information seeking and information use. The author further states, that users actively seek current information from the various media available in libraries such as journals and more currently, electronic media. According to Singh and Satija (2016), information seeking is a basic activity indulged in by all people and manifested through a particular way of behavior. It is an aspect of scholarly work most interesting to academic libraries who strive to develop collections services and organizational structures that facilitate seeking of information. To Ukpebor (2011), information seeking behavior is an area of dynamic interest among librarians, information scientist, communication scientists, sociologist and psychologists. Information users make active and intentional attempts to seek up to date information from the library resources.

2.2. THEORETICAL AND EMPIRICAL STUDIES

Neuroticism as described by Widiger and Oltmanns (2017), is that tendency that one can easily experience unpleasant emotion such as anger, anxiety, fear, guilt, depression, impulsive, and vulnerability for one reason or the other. The implication is that academic librarians with these traits on the high side are likely to show a level of worries, insecure, self-conscious, anxiety and general distressed among others. Whereas, those that with low tendency tend to be relaxed, calm, self-satisfied and unemotional. Lofti, Muktar, Ologbo and Chiemeké (2016) posit that neuroticism encompasses various negative dispositions namely sadness, nervousness and horridness and involves negative emotions like anger, anxiety, depression that have negative influence on information seeking behaviour. The assumption therefore is that academic librarians who are high on neuroticism would not be at their best when seeking information due to these negative emotions on the ground that these emotions will act as barrier to their successful information seeking. On the other hand academic librarians who are in control their emotions are usually calm, relaxed, and easy or less neurotic, can satisfy information retrieval urge and can resolve most barriers faced in the cause of their information seeking process.

As noted by Heinstrom (2003), negative emotions consume energy and distract concentration. This implies that a high level neurotic librarian cannot critically evaluate the information before actually using

it or providing it to others. The characteristics of neurotic trait can apply to all manner of staff. Any staff, with librarians inclusive that is high in neuroticism trait display anxiety, depression, anger, fearfulness and insecurity mood in public and may not have enough time to critically analyze and evaluate document before retrieving and using it due to their neurotic tendencies or negative emotions. Such staff is also often distracted and lack concentration.

There have been number of studies on this issue outside Nigeria. For instance, Hydegard (2009) carried out a study on personality traits and group-based information behaviour as an exploratory study on three (3) voluntary groups of ten (10) Royal School of Library and Information Science lecturers in Denmark. The study made use of the big-five personality dimensions to measure how personality traits can influence information seeking behaviour in a group situation. The study was guided by three (3) research questions. Three instruments were used for data collection which were; questionnaire, diaries and interview. Data collected was analyzed using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that in a group work situation, neuroticism does not have much influence but tended to be more present in individual work situation or responsibility

According to Dinet (2016), several variables affect information seeking behavior of an individual. Some of them include contextual variables, resources variables, and individual's variables. Emotions form a part of the individual variables that play a key role in the determination of information seeking behaviour of an individual. Dinet (2016) highlights the role of effective elements in information-seeking behavior, physical and/or cognitive actions and strategies used in dealing with unique feature of the problem associated with the search for information. These highlighted roles of emotions include; frustration, anxiety, and uncertainty in the information seeking process. While Wang and Yang (2007) investigated the correlation between anxiety and performance of learners in information search tasks, the role of emotional factors on information retrieval and literacy. The author observed that the psychodynamics of individual's information behaviour depend on their personality and social competence. Consequently, the emotional status of the individuals can contribute towards several outcomes such as search process problems, information adjustment problems, and personal information (Matteson, 2017). The process of identifying information need, locating the relevant information, making sense of the information, and using the information is associated to a plethora of emotions.

An empirical study on lecturers on the same emotional issue by Lisa (2017) identified a set of micro and macro level events that resulted in either negative or positive emotions. The events causing emotions such as sadness, fear, alienation, joy, and surprise affected the lecturers' ability of searching for information and completing their assignments. A parallel study evaluated the socio-emotional development of lecturers and their information literacy competence. The study found that emotional resilience and socio-emotional maturity affected the information literacy competence of the lecturers. According to Matteson (2017), emotional intelligence entails the ability of an individual to monitor their emotions and feelings while discriminating them and using the information to guide one's actions. The author further states that emotional intelligence involves the perception of emotions, use of the emotions

to facilitate thinking, understanding the emotions, and managing the emotions and that individuals portray varying capability of processing information based on their emotional nature.

Kuhlthau (2017) reveals specific emotions associated with the process of searching for information. According to the author, uncertainty is the principle emotions for information seeking. The author defines uncertainty as the cognitive state that causes effective symptoms such as lack of confidence and anxiety. Anxiety and uncertainty characterize the initial phases of the process of searching for information. The effective indications of uncertainty, confusion lead to vague and imprecise thoughts regarding a problem or topic. However, a shift to focused knowledge leads to a decline in uncertainty and increase in confidence. Kuhlthau (2017) asserts that the uncertainty associated with a gap in meaning, limited construct or lack of understanding initiates the information seeking process. Complex situations associated with information search were linked to uncertainty.

However, Kalbach (2014) observes that the perceptions of complexity rather than the objective complexity of the situation cause the feeling of uncertainty rather; Wilson (2015) confirmed the observation through his 'Uncertainty Principle'. The author relates the effect of emotions on information seeking behavior to personality traits. He uses the five factors model to explain the five main emotional factors that affect high levels of neuroticism that indicate a high probability of experiencing negative emotions while low levels of neuroticism indicate a high probability of experiencing negative emotions while low levels of neuroticism indicate emotional stability. Neuroticism heightens the probability of developing emotions such as anxiety. Highly neurotic individuals have a high likelihood of becoming sad, temperamental, unstable and worried. The vagueness of information frustrates a highly neurotic person during the initial search. Essentially, neuroticism leads to nervousness and negative affectivity during the search for information. While focusing on online search for information, Lopatovska (2017) highlights the relationship between emotional experiences and the information seeking behaviour and process. Neuroticism is also associated with a diminished quality of life, including feelings of ill-will, excessive worry, occupational failure, and marital dissatisfaction (Oze, Benet-Martinez & Annu (2006). High levels of neuroticism will contribute to poor work performance due to emotional preoccupation, exhaustion, and distraction.

The state of the user before engaging in an active information search affects his or her emotional experiences. The state depends on individual characteristics, cultural background, as well attitudes and moods towards the search. Emotions affect behaviours such as the strategies used in the search, the search performance acquired. A successful or unsuccessful completion of the search influences the emotional experiences, which, in turn determine whether the user continues or terminates the search. Onwuegbuzie and Jiao (2004) also found in the library, that anxiety among students affects their information search and performance negatively. Many studies have also been conducted to evaluate the effect of emotion on users' information seeking behaviour. According to the author, emotional factors affect search strategies and performance, search results, motivation, and satisfaction. Nahl (2017) analyzed information behavior from the literature on affective and cognitive components of

searching. The author found a positive relationship between affective variables and satisfaction, performance, and motivation. The author studied the influence of affective variables on information seeking behavior and found that emotions such as optimism and self-efficacy countered negative emotions such as frustration and irritation, which are associated with uncertainty.

However, Wang and Yang (2007) found a reciprocal relationship between affective variables and search performance. The findings indicate that positive feelings instigate further search while negative feelings hinder it. The author also investigated the cognitive and affective aspects of information seeking behavior among novice users. The study found that the need for confirmation, hesitation, surprise, and fear affect the strategies that the users applied in the search process. For instance, the study found that the need for confirmation provide users with incessant motivation to continue their search while surprise initiates the process of reconciliation of the search expectations and reality. Butler and Cartier (2015) investigated the effects of emotions on processes such as reading, writing, researching and presenting. The study found that low interest in the process, low self-esteem, and high stress levels led to avoidance, which affects the processes negatively. According to Hughes (2005) a common challenge facing the information seeking behaviour among university lecturers is the ability to access and select the relevant information when needed. Various challenges increase the complexity of searching relevant information. Consequently, the information seeking behaviour may be affected by self-confidence, emotions, and understanding of the problem. Liu and Redfarn (2015) investigated the behavior of multicultural lecturers at Sa Jose State University. Using a questionnaire, the researchers sought to understand the effect of length of stay on the confidence of the lecturers in seeking help from the reference desk. The study found that lecturers who had used the library for over fifteen years had high levels of confidence and often sought help from the reference desk.

Suriya, Sangeetha and Nambi (2004) carried out a research work on information seeking behavior of faculty members in university, Cuddalore District. The purpose of their study was to investigate how faculty members seek information from the library. It was mentioned that most of the respondents 61(38.12%) visited the library several times a week to meet their information needs. Shokean and Kushik (2002) studied about information seeking behaviour of social scientists working in the university located in Haryana. They reported that most of the social scientists visit the library daily.

3.0. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive research design. Using purposive sampling technique, 665 academic librarians from 42 federal universities in Nigeria were selected as the sampled population while a self-constructed questionnaire titled, Neuroticism and Information Seeking behavior of Academic Librarian questionnaire (NISBALQ) was the major instrument used for data collection A total of 665 questionnaires were administered through electronic mail system with the aid of research assistants from each of the 42 universities and luckily, the whole 665 questionnaires were completed and returned

showing 100% response. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics tools of frequency, percentage and mean and presented in tables while the null hypothesis (H01) was testing using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis of the correlation coefficient at a 0.05 level of significance.

4.0. PRESENTATION OF DATA

Research Question 1

What factors influence information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in studied federal universities?

Table 1 - Factors that influence information seeking behavior of academic librarians in these federal universities

Items	SA		A		DA		SDA		Decision
	F	&	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Self-confidence	213	32	452	68	**	**	**	**	Accepted
Emotions	138	20.7	107	16.1	266	40	154	23.2	Rejected
Understanding of the problem	399	60	266	40	**	**	**	**	Accepted
Articulation of needs	237	35.6	202	30.4	185	27.83	41	6.17	Accepted
Availability of information	412	62	67	10	120	18	67	10	Accepted
Time frame	165	24.8	375	56.4	90	13.5	35	5.3	Accepted
Personal research interest	555	83	110	17	**	**	**	**	Accepted

Key- *SA=Strongly Agreed, *A=Agreed, DA=Disagreed, *SDA=Strongly Disagreed

The data in table 1 highlights some factors that influence information seeking behavior of academic librarians in the federal universities. The data show that the 665 respondents representing 100% strongly agreed or agreed that self-confidence, understanding of the problem and personal research interest are the main factors that influence their information seeking behavior, 540 respondents or 81.2% strongly agreed or agreed that it is the time frame whereas, 477 or 72% strongly agreed or agreed that they are influenced by the availability of information and 66% or 439 respondents strongly agreed or agreed that they are been influenced by the articulation of needs. On the contrary, 420

respondents or 63.2% strongly disagreed or disagreed that emotions influence their information seeking behavior.

Research Question 2

What are the challenges of information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in the federal universities?

Table 2: Mean Values of the challenges of information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in the federal universities

Item	SA		A		D		SD		Total	Mean Value	Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
My age affects my information needs	380	57	182	27.3	62	9.3	40	6	665	3.35	Significant
My gender does not give me the opportunity to search information I need	66	10	36	5.4	340	51.1	223	33.5	665	1.92	NS
The curriculum of my academic discipline affects my information needs	280	42	315	47.4	44	6.6	26	4	665	3.27	Significant
My rank does affect my information needs	489	88	100	15	45	6.8	31	4.7	665	3.48	Significant
My research areas affect my information needs	371	55.8	250	37.6	35	5	11	1.6	665	3.21	Significant
Significant mean value = 3.05											

The data as disclosed in table 2 above show that 589 of the 665 sampled population representing 88.6% strongly agreed or agreed that their ranks affect their information seeking behavior, 84.5% or 562 respondents strongly agreed or agreed that their information seeking behavior is influenced by their age, while 595 or 89.4% of the respondents strongly agreed or agreed that their information seeking behavior is influenced by the curriculum of their academic discipline while area of research influences 621 respondents or 93.4%. On the other hand, 563 or 84.7% of the respondents strongly disagreed or disagreed that their gender influences their information seeking behaviour.

Furthermore from the significant mean value of 3.05 with a benchmark of 2.50 as shown in Table 2, my age affects my information needs (X=3.35), the curriculum of my academic discipline affects my information needs (X=3.27), my rank does affect my information needs (X=3.48) and my research areas affect my information needs (X=3.21). Whereas, my gender does not give me the opportunity to search information I need (X=2.00) responses were in the negative. The analysis shows that age, gender,

academic discipline and rank significantly influence information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in the federal universities.

Research Question 3

What are the Neuroticism traits displayed by academic librarians in the federal universities in their information seeking behaviour?

Table 3: Neuroticism traits displayed by academic librarians in federal universities in Nigeria in their information seeking behaviour

Item	SA		A		DA		SDA		Decision
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
I get angry so easily in my search for information when the needed information is not accessed.	109	16.4	26	3.9	230	34.6	300	45.1	In-between
I am self-consciousness when searching for information.	413	62.1	252	37.9	**	**	**	**	Agreed
I am easily irritated.	105	15.7	45	6.8	210	31.6	305	45.9	Disagreed
I have the challenge of emotional instability.	266	40	154	23.1	138	20.8	107	16.1	Agreed
I go into depression if I fail to get needed information.	7	1	20	3	312	47	328	49	Disagreed
I respond poorly to environmental stress.	211	31.7	196	29.5	107	16.1	101	15.2	Agreed
I interpret ordinary situations as threatening					305	45.9	360	54.1	Disagreed
I can experience minor frustrations as hopelessly overwhelming.	50	7.5	65	9.8	215	32.3	335	50.4	Disagreed

Data as contain in table 3 indicate neuroticism traits displayed by academic librarians in federal universities in their information seeking behaviour. The data show that 100% or 665 respondents strongly agreed or agreed that they are self-conscious when searching for information, 330 or 63.1% of the respondents strongly agreed or agreed that they have the challenge of emotional stability while 407 of the respondents or 61.2% strongly agreed or agreed that they respond poorly to environmental stress. Furtherance, 20.3% representing 135 respondent strongly agreed or agreed that they get angry

so easily when the needed information is not accessed while other items in the table were higher on strongly disagreed or disagreed.

Research Question 4

What is the correlation between neuroticism and information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in federal universities?

Table 4: Mean Responses on Neuroticism and Information Seeking Behaviour of academic librarians

S/N	Neuroticism and Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Librarians	SA		A		DA		SDA		Total	Mean Value	Decision
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%			
a.	I am forceful when seeking information	110	16.6	96	14.4	240	36.1	229	34.4	665	2.16	NS
b.	I can be tensed in information seeking	234	35.2	232	35	100	15	99	14.8	665	2.90	Significant
c.	I argue a lot while seeking information	204	30.7	206	31	144	21.6	111	16.7	665	2.76	Significant
d.	I do not feel sad in information seeking	313	47.1	187	28	125	18.8	40	6	665	3.16	Significant
e.	I am always rude to others in information seeking	78	11.8	74	11.2	299	34.4	213	32	665	1.81	NS
	Significant Mean Value =2.56											

Table 4 shows the mean responses on Neuroticism and Information Seeking Behaviour of academic librarians in the studied federal universities. From the available data as displayed in table 4, three items mean value are greater than the significant mean value ($X=2.65$) The data show that 'I can be tensed in information' has a mean (X) value of 2.90 with 436 respondents or 70.2% strongly agreed or agreed on it, 'I argue a lot while seeking information' has a mean (X) value of 2.76 with 61.7% of the respondents strongly agreed or agreed on it while 'I do not feel sad in information seeking' with highest mean (X) value of 3.16 had a strongly agreed or agreed responses of 75.1% representing 500 respondents. On the other hand, the other two reasons namely; 'I am forceful when seeking information' ($X=2.16$) and 'I am always rude to others in information seeking' ($X=1.81$) mean were less than the significant mean value ($X=2.56$). The significant mean value ($X=2.56$) did show that neuroticism has positive correlation with information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in the studied federal universities.

H01. There is no statistical significant ($p>0.5$) correlation between Neuroticism and information seeking behavior of academic librarians in federal universities.

Table 5: Correlation between Neuroticism and information seeking behavior of academic librarians in the studied federal universities

Variables	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	R	Sig	Remark
Neuroticism	665	4.42	72	0.08	0.05	Significant
Information seeking Behavior	665	4.11	69			

The data in table 5 is a summarized Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis of the correlation coefficient between Neuroticism and information seeking behavior of academic librarians in the federal universities. The outcome of the test shows that there is a statistical significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation between Neuroticism and Information seeking Behavior of academic librarians in the studied federal universities ($r = 0.08$). The implication is that from the data available, there is not sufficient evidence to back-up the null hypothesis and for this reason, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected. This indicates that Neuroticism significantly correlates with information seeking behavior of academic librarians positively.

5.1. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

On the factors that influence information seeking behavior of academic librarians in the studied federal universities, the outcome of this study has shown that there are many factors that influence information seeking behavior of academic librarians. These factors as discovered include, self-confidence, understanding of the problem and personality. Others are research interest, the articulation of needs, time frame as well as the availability of information (see table 1). This finding buttresses the finding of Dinet (2016) who stated that several variables affect information seeking behavior of an individual which include contextual variables, resources variables, and individual's variables and that emotions form a part of the individual variables that play a key role in the determination of information seeking behaviour of an individual. Although in the finding of this study, emotions was no significant as only 36.8% strongly agreed or agreed to it as a factor that influences their information seeking behaviour while on the other part, it may be deemed a contributing factor considering the percentage that affirmed to it.

The study also identified some factors posing as challenges to the information seeking behaviour of the academic librarians. As shown in table 2, such factors as analyzed include age, gender, academic discipline and rank. It is pertinent to state that these challenges may not be limited to the ones identified in this study. All the same, the result shows that these factors significantly influence information seeking behaviour of the academic librarians. This outcome is in conformity with the finding of Matteson (2017) who investigated the correlation between anxiety and performance of learners in information search tasks, the role of emotional factors on information retrieval and literacy and observed that the psychodynamics of individual's information behaviour depends on their personality and social competence. Consequently, the emotional status of the individuals can contribute towards several

outcomes such as; search process problems, information adjustment problems, and personal information

The study also found some of neuroticism related traits displayed by the academic librarians in their information seeking behaviour. These found traits as shown in table 3 among others are, self-consciousness, anger, emotional instability and stress. Some of them also display certain degree of irritation, and frustrations while sign of depression is so insignificant. This finding, reveals that neuroticism was significant in the information seeking behaviour of the academic librarians. The implication is that neuroticism significantly affects information seeking behaviour of the academic librarians. This is because neuroticism comprises of negative dispositions which could have negative effect on academic librarians' information seeking behaviour. These negative emotions do act as barrier to academic librarians' fruitful search for information as with high neuroticism little or no success would be achieved when searching for information.

The result collaborates the findings of Hienstrom (2003) and Muktar, Ologbo, and Chiemeké (2016) who in their separate studies found that neuroticism encompasses negative emotions like anger, anxiety and depression and could have negative influence on information seeking behaviour of lecturers. They also argued that negative emotions consume energy and distracts concentration due to the fact that high leveled neurotic students do not critically evaluate information before actually using it and individuals with high neuroticism would probably be less involved in information seeking. This outcome also agrees with Gul, Shah, Mahajan, and Tun-Nisa (2014) who in their study revealed that neuroticism negatively influences information seeking behaviour of students. They noted that neuroticism students are often influenced by negative emotions such as anger, fear, embarrassment, guilt, depression and sadness and these hinders successful information search and retrieval. Invariably, academic librarians with negative emotion may often be hostile, self-conscious, anxious, insecure and moody.

Furtherance, the study also discovered based on analyzed data in table 4 with a significant mean value ($X=2.56$) that neuroticism has positive correlation with information seeking behaviour of academic librarians in the studied federal universities. Above all, the summarized Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis of the correlation coefficient between Neuroticism and information seeking behavior of the academic librarians further buttressed that there is a statistical significant ($p<0.05$) correlation between Neuroticism and Information seeking Behavior of the academic librarians ($r=0.08$). The finding also agrees with Halder, Roy and Chakraborty (2010) who found correlation between neuroticism and information seeking behaviour. The result also concurs with Hienstrom (2014) that found individuals with high neuroticism, to be worriers and anxious in information seeking. In his studies, Gupta (2008) noted that the reason why information seeking would be interfered by neuroticism is due to the negative attributes associated with it. Individuals who have high neuroticism are characterized as insecure, moody and self-conscious. They possess the common inclination to express undesirable attributes such as embarrassment, fear, sadness, anger, and guiltiness. On the other hand, this result is contrary to that of Wang and Yang (2007) who in their study found that there is no significant

correlation between neuroticism and information seeking behaviour. The result of this research may be attributed to the fact that people with neurotic tendency are prone to negative emotions like anger, stress, moody, fear and depression among other traits

5.2. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The result of this study did show that there is significant correlation between neuroticism and information seeking behaviour of the academic librarians. It is paramount that academic librarians as custodians of knowledge and information scientists should be conversant with certain personality traits like neuroticism and ways through which they could affect their information seeking behaviors. This no doubt, will place them in better position to tackle such challenges and render effective and efficient services to both the general users of the library and faculty members of their universities. Going by the findings therefore, the study makes the following recommendation:

1. Management of university libraries should make provision for a separate section of library equipped with state of the art facilities exclusively for academic librarians for effective research and to enhance their academic activities.
2. Information is not a luxury but a necessary tool upon which all sound decisions are based. Therefore, current information materials should be made available in both print and e-format to academic librarians in order to enhance their academic activities.
3. The working hours of academic librarians should be adjusted to accommodate their personal responsibilities as a way of easing work created stress.
4. Academic librarians work schedule should be made flexible in such a way that it will allow them, to attend to their personal needs to avoid depression
5. The challenge of inadequacy in the number academic librarians employed resulting to job overload, should be resolved by employing desirable number of academic librarians.

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